

**INCLUSIVE EDUCATIONAL PROCESSES FOR CHILDREN WITH HEARING
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Abstract. This study examines the specific features of organizing a special educational environment for children with hearing impairments. A general description of the means and methods of organizing inclusive education, as well as the conditions created for children with disabilities in our country, is given, and great attention is paid to finding a place in social life by educating children with disabilities together with healthy children.

Keywords: surdopedagogy, rehabilitation, hearing function, integration, socialization, social isolation, inclusive, competence, speech therapist.

**ESHITISHDA NUQSONI BOR BOLALAR UCHUN INKLYUZIV TA'LIM
JARAYONLARI**

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqotda eshitish qobiliyati buzilgan bolalar uchun maxsus ta'lim muhitini tashkil etishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari ko'rib chiqiladi. Inklyuziv ta'limni tashkil etish vositalari, usullari va yurtimizdagi imkoniyati cheklangan bolalar hamda ular uchun yaratilayotgan barcha shart-sharoitlar, nuqsoni bor bolalarni sog'lom bolalar bilan birga o'qitish orqali ijtimoiy hayotda o'z o'rnini topishga katta e'tibor berilayotgani haqida umumiy tavsif berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: surdopedagogika, reabilitatsiya, eshitish funktsiyasi, integratsiya, ijtimoiylashtirish, ijtimoiy izolyatsiya, inklyuziv, kompetensiya, logoped.

**ИНКЛЮЗИВНЫЕ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫЕ ПРОЦЕССЫ ДЛЯ ДЕТЕЙ С
НАРУШЕНИЯМИ СЛУХА**

Аннотация. В данном исследовании рассматриваются особенности организации специальной образовательной среды для детей с нарушениями слуха. Дана общая характеристика средств и методов организации инклюзивного образования,

условий, созданных для детей с ограниченными возможностями в нашей стране, а также большого внимания, уделяемого поиску их места в общественной жизни путем совместного обучения детей с ограниченными возможностями со здоровыми детьми.

Ключевые слова: сурдопедагогика, реабилитация, слуховая функция, интеграция, социализация, социальная изоляция, инклюзивность, компетентность, логопед.

Introduction

Today, a number of reforms are being implemented in our Republic. At the heart of all reforms, first of all, is the main urgent issue of raising children who can grow up as well-rounded individuals, grow up no less than anyone else, and conquer the world arena. Social protection of children with disabilities, developmental disabilities, and orphans left without parental care is always an urgent task of society. In order to implement this task, a number of works are being carried out in our Republic to ensure the rights and freedoms of children with disabilities, create the necessary conditions, eliminate restrictions in their life activities, and organize education for them. The work of each organ in the human body is closely interconnected. And the healthy functioning of the body organs is a beautiful miracle in human life. Just as each organ has its own place and function, our ear and hearing ability also occupy a high place in our lives. As we know, the science of surdopedagogy is a science that studies children with hearing impairments, and the main tasks of surdopedagogy are to comprehensively study children with hearing impairments from a pedagogical perspective, improve language teaching in special schools, develop hearing abilities and form pronunciation, and study the laws of education and upbringing of children with hearing impairments and apply these laws in the lives of children. In addition, it is to increase the efficiency of the development system of auditory perception, achieve work in a certain professional field for children with hearing impairments, improve technical means of teaching, ensure the continuity of kindergarten and school education, coordinate the work of medical and public education sectors across the republic, and study the problems of early diagnosis. Educational institutions for children and adults with hearing impairments are built on the basis of unity and continuity of its links, each stage of which fulfills its tasks and is at the same time interconnected with the next. One of the conditions for high-quality education, upbringing, development and rehabilitation of people with hearing impairments is a correct understanding of the characteristics of the state of hearing function by each specialist and

their consideration in the system of all types of psychological and mental illnesses. The number of children with disabilities is increasing. This negative trend requires the creation of special conditions in kindergartens, general education schools, as well as in special schools, which will provide a comfortable environment for children with special needs and ensure their successful integration into the social environment. The creation of all necessary conditions for full education of schoolchildren with hearing impairments, taking into account all the features of their individual development, is one of the main goals in the field of wide implementation of the rights of both deaf and hard of hearing children to education. "It is necessary to develop and apply special forms of education, upbringing and socialization of such children. The use of special methods and forms of education should help to successfully overcome social isolation and contribute to the rehabilitation and socialization of children with disabilities." Inclusive education involves the organization of joint education of children with special needs and their peers. At the same time, children who receive education and upbringing in accordance with their educational needs can study in general schools and preschool institutions, learn to actively interact with each other, and develop comprehensively together with children of all categories of their age. When considering an inclusive education option for their child, parents should have complete information about the features of a particular model of inclusive education, the child's prospects for education in an environment of normally developing peers, possible difficulties and ways to solve them. The main tasks of psychological, medical and pedagogical support for a child with hearing impairment in inclusive conditions are:

- assistance (support) to the child in solving urgent problems of development, education, socialization;
- assistance in drawing up, implementing and evaluating the effectiveness of the implementation of an individual development plan for the student;
- formation of psychological and pedagogical competence (psychological culture) of students, parents, pedagogical staff.

Within the framework of the specified tasks, psychological, medical and pedagogical support carries out the following main directions:

- psychological and pedagogical diagnostics of students with hearing impairments in inclusive settings;
- consulting teachers working with the child, the child's parents, parents of normally developing peers studying in the same class as a child with hearing impairment.

- organization of correctional and developmental work with the child (speech therapist, special education teacher, teacher-psychologist).

- organization of correctional and developmental work with the child (speech therapist, special education teacher, teacher-psychologist). In addition, classes can be organized at school or in an organization that acts as a resource center and participates in the program of psychological, medical and pedagogical support for a child with hearing impairment in inclusive settings.

- examination (educational and educational programs, projects, teaching aids, educational environment, professional activities of specialists of educational institutions).

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be said that the organization of inclusive education improves the social life of children with hearing impairments, without exaggeration. Thus, a distinctive feature of the development of speech and literacy of children with hearing impairments in the context of inclusive education is the organization of flexible educational conditions that help children with hearing impairments accumulate their own experience of successful activities, which is a certain incentive for their further development, social adaptation and successful self-management in life.

Used literature:

1. Turemuratova, Aziza, Rita Kurbanova, and Barno Saidboyeva. "EDUCATIONAL TRADITIONS IN SHAPING THE WORLDVIEW OF YOUNG PEOPLE IN FOLK PEDAGOGY." *Modern Science and Research* 2.10 (2023): 318-322.
2. Kurbanova, R. J., and B. E. Saidboeva. "MAKTAB VA OILADA ESTETIK TARBIYANI SHAKLLANTIRISH JARAYONIDA O'QUVCHILARNING AKSIOLOGIK DUNYOQARASHINI RIVOJLANTIRISH." *Inter education & global study* 9 (2024): 114-121.
3. Jarasovna, Kurbanova Rita. "The Role of National Values in Shaping the Aesthetic Worldview of Schoolchildren." *International Journal of Pedagogics* 5.03 (2025): 55-58.
4. Jarilkapovich, Matjanov Aman. "USE OF PEDAGOGICAL METHODS BASED ON THE MODERN EDUCATIONAL PROGRAM TO INCREASE THE EFFECTIVENESS OF EDUCATION." *European International Journal of Pedagogics* 4.06 (2024): 26-33.

5. Jarilkapovich, Matjanov Aman. "Program Technology for Choosing an Effective Educational Methodology Based on Modern Pedagogical Research in The Educational System." *CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGICS* 6.02 (2025): 30-33.
6. Turemuratova, Aziza, Shahlo Matmuratova, and Nargisa Tajieva. "THE DEPENDENCE OF MULTI-VECTOR APPROACHES ON PEDAGOGICAL METHODS AND PSYCHOLOGICAL TRAINING IN IMPROVING STUDENTS'COLLABORATIVE SKILLS BASED ON THE EDUCATIONAL PROGRAM." *Modern Science and Research* 4.4 (2025): 50-55.
7. Aziza, Turemuratova. "KONFLIKT VA UNING KELIB CHIQISH SABABLARI." *Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке* 3.32 (2025): 457-459.
8. Begibaevna, Turemuratova Aziza. "PSYCHOLOGICAL CONFIDENTIALITY OF THE FORMATION OF STUDENTS'COLLABORATIVE SKILLS BASED ON MULTI-VECTOR APPROACHES IN EDUCATION." (2025).
9. Turemuratova, Aziza, Azamat Utambetov, and Rinat Seytimov. "PSIXOLOGIK TRENING ASOSLARI TUSHUNCHASI VA O'SMIRLARNING KOLLOBORATIV KO'NIKMALARINI OSHIRUVCHI PSIXOLOGIK TRENINGLAR." *Modern Science and Research* 4.4 (2025): 135-141.
10. Turemuratova, Aziza, Farog'at Seytmambetova, and Nazokat Masharipova. "PSIXOLOGIK TRENINGLARNING USLUBIY MUMMOLARI VA KOLLOBORATIV TA'LIMDA GURUH MUAMMOLARI." *Modern Science and Research* 4.4 (2025): 100-106.
11. Begibaevna, Turemuratova Aziza, and Turganbayeva Amina Quanishbayevna. "PSIXOLOG TRENERNING KASBIY KO'NIKMALARI VA PSIXOLOGIK SALOHIYATINI OSHIRUVCHI AMALIY TRENINGLAR." (2025).
12. Turemuratova, Aziza, Aynisa Jaqsimuratova, and Ramiza Mustapaeva. "SELF-CONTROL RULES OF A PSYCHOLOGIST-TRAINER." *Modern Science and Research* 4.4 (2025): 217-221.
13. Muratbayevna, Dauletova Gozal, and Madaminova Nargiza Qurbanbayevna. "BOLANING RIVOJLANISH DAVRI PSIXOLOGIYASI." *Scientific Impulse* 1 (2022): 33-35.

14. Reyimbaevna, Mambetiyarova Venera, and Jumabayeva Marupa. "OTA-ONA VA FARZANDLAR MUNOSABATINING XUSUSIYATLARI." TADQIQOTLAR. UZ 51 (2024): 20-23.